

1 **Latest Pleistocene to Holocene loess in the central Great Plains:**
2 **Optically stimulated luminescence dating and multi-proxy analysis of the**
3 **Enders loess section (Nebraska, USA)**

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56
57 **Abstract**

58 Loess deposits of the central Great Plains, USA, and their intercalated soils provide a detailed
59 record of climatically driven changes within the aeolian system during the Pleistocene-
60 Holocene transition and the Holocene. Here we present a detailed optically stimulated
61 luminescence (OSL) chronology as well as multi-proxy analysis obtained for the first time on
62 the Enders section, located in southwestern Nebraska, central Great Plains. The section records
63 multiple episodes of rapid loess deposition alternating with soil formation. Rapid accumulation
64 of Late Pleistocene Peoria Loess was replaced around 13-14 ka by formation of the Brady Soil
65 until 9.5 ± 0.6 ka. The Holocene Bignell Loess then buried the Brady Soil and accumulated
66 episodically throughout the Holocene. The loess-paleosol stratigraphy since the Late
67 Pleistocene at the Enders site is very similar to that at other sites in western Nebraska, and the
68 newly developed OSL chronology (based on three grain size classes) adds new confidence to
69 earlier dating. The high-resolution grain size profile from Enders shares many features with
70 similar data from the previously studied Wauneta site, including three peaks of fine-grained
71 material just above and within the Brady Soil, likely representing response to millennial-scale
72 climatic changes during the Pleistocene-Holocene transition. This study demonstrates the
73 potential for developing high-resolution, well-dated paleoclimatic records from the loess of the
74 central Great Plains. Contrasts between Great Plains and Eurasian loess records reflect
75 differences in the Late Pleistocene to Holocene climatic evolution and other factors influencing
76 the loess system.

77 **Keywords:** Holocene; loess; optically stimulated luminescence dating; grain size; magnetic
78 susceptibility; stable isotopes; Brady Soil

79
80 **1. Introduction**

81 Loess is the most extensive surficial deposit in the central United States (**Aleinikoff et al.,**
82 **2008**), and is especially thick in Nebraska, in the central Great Plains of North America. The

83 last-glacial Peoria loess reaches its greatest thickness in Nebraska (**Roberts et al., 2003; Muhset**
84 **al., 2008**). Above the Peoria Loess, the stratigraphic framework of the late Quaternary in the
85 central Great Plains also includes the Holocene Bignell Loess (**Schultz and Stout, 1948; Maat**
86 **and Johnson, 1996**), holding the potential to capture an unprecedented Holocene record of
87 climatically driven soil formation and loess deposition (**Miao et al., 2007b**). Provenance studies
88 indicate that much of the Peoria and Bignell Loess in western Nebraska is dryland dust derived
89 from unglaciated areas to the northwest of the major loess deposits (**Aleinikoff et al., 2008;**
90 **Yang et al., 2017**). These studies imply that regional Late Pleistocene to Holocene loess
91 stratigraphy is likely to record a relatively direct response of the aeolian system to climatic
92 change rather than shifts in source area or glacial advance and retreat. Local variations in the
93 regional pattern are clearly possible, however, related to patchy vegetation cover or local
94 geomorphic controls, particularly since much of the Bignell Loess is likely derived from local
95 sources including the aeolian reworking of Peoria Loess (**Mason et al., 2003; Yang et al., 2017**).

96 Peoria Loess was deposited during the peak of the last glacial period (largely in Marine
97 Isotope Stage 2) and is up to 50 m thick in western Nebraska (**Maat and Johnson, 1996;**
98 **Johnson and Willey, 2000; Roberts et al., 2003**). Radiocarbon, thermoluminescence (TL), and
99 optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) data indicate that the onset of Peoria Loess
100 accumulation was about 25 ± 3 ka (exact dates varying by site and dating method), and
101 accumulation ended with the slowdown in sedimentation that allowed formation of the well-
102 expressed Brady Soil during the Pleistocene-Holocene transition (**Martin, 1993; May and**
103 **Holen, 1993; Maat and Johnson, 1996; Roberts et al., 2003; Mason et al., 2008; Pigati et al.,**
104 **2013**). The Brady Soil is overlain by the Bignell Loess (**Schultz and Stout, 1948; Jacobs and**
105 **Mason, 2004**).

106 Previous research at numerous sites across the central Great Plains has documented the
107 basic stratigraphy and chronology of the uppermost Peoria Loess-Brady Soil-Bignell Loess
108 sequence and correlations with broad-scale climatic change (**Johnson and Willey, 2000; Mason**
109 **and Kuzila, 2000; Roberts et al., 2003; Mason et al., 2003; Jacobs and Mason, 2004; Miao**
110 **et al., 2005, 2007a, b; Marín-Spiotta et al., 2014; Mason et al., 2008; Muhs et al., 2008;**
111 **Woodburn et al., 2017**). The Brady Soil formed due to relatively high effective moisture that
112 reduced dust influx and enhanced pedogenic processes by slowing surface upbuilding (**Johnson**
113 **and Willey, 2000; Jacobs and Mason, 2004**). Radiocarbon ages on organic matter from the

114 Brady Soil and OSL ages just below and above it from numerous sites suggest that it began
115 forming after a reduction in loess accumulation rate between 15 and 13.5 ka and it was buried by
116 renewed loess deposition between 10.5 and 9 ka (**Martin, 1993; Maat and Johnson, 1996;**
117 **Muhs et al., 1999; Johnson and Willey, 2000; Mason and Kuzila, 2000; Miao et al., 2005;**
118 **2007a, b; Mason et al., 2008**). Thus, Brady Soil formation typically spanned all or part of the
119 Bølling-Allerød (approximately 14.7–12.9 cal ka) and the Younger Dryas (12.9–11.5 cal ka)
120 (**Mason et al., 2008**). The Brady Soil is morphologically well expressed, typically with A/Bk/C
121 horization, in thick stratigraphic sections where it is isolated from the modern surface by
122 several meters of loess (**Jacobs and Mason, 2007**).

123 In the central Great Plains, Bignell Loess sections provide a near-continuous record of
124 Holocene paleoclimatic change (**Pye et al., 1995; Johnson and Willey, 2000; Mason and**
125 **Kuzila, 2000; Mason et al., 2003; Miao et al., 2005**). Periods of greater Holocene loess
126 accumulation correspond to intervals of widespread dune activation in the surrounding region,
127 most notably at ca. 10-6 ka, 4-2.3 ka, and 1.1 to 0.7 ka (Medieval Climatic Anomaly) (**Miao et**
128 **al., 2007b**). These intervals can also be identified as periods of dry climate in areas surrounding
129 the Great Plains in reconstructions based on dendroclimatology, speleothem records, lake-level
130 changes, and pollen data (e.g. **Cook et al., 2004; Denniston et al., 2007; Shuman and**
131 **Marsicek, 2016**) although comparisons among those studies and the aeolian record also suggest
132 considerable spatial variability and/or inconsistency between paleoclimatic proxies. The
133 uppermost Bignell Loess is < 1000 yr old (**Mason et al., 2003; Miao et al., 2007b**). Bignell
134 Loess may contain multiple buried soils (**Mason and Kuzila, 2000; Jacobs and Mason, 2004**).
135 In western and central Nebraska, Bignell Loess is thickest at the downwind margins of dune
136 fields, (up to 6 m thick at the Wauneta site, **Figure 1**) (**Mason et al., 2003; Jacobs and Mason,**
137 **2004**). On the other hand, on stable uplands farther from the loess sources Bignell Loess is thin
138 and incorporated into the surface soil profile (**Jacobs and Mason, 2007**).

139 Stable isotope analyses of organic matter in loess and buried soils at the Wauneta site and
140 other localities have documented Late Pleistocene to Holocene vegetation change in the central
141 Great Plains (**Muhs et al., 1999; Johnson and Willey, 2000; Feggestad et al., 2004; Miao et**
142 **al., 2007a**). Phytolith analysis and organic matter geochemical investigations at the Wauneta site
143 added detail on vegetation change that could not be resolved by stable isotopic records alone
144 (**Marín-Spiotta et al., 2014; Woodburn et al., 2017**). These results indicate that grassland,

145 dominated by cool-season grasses (using the C₃ photosynthetic pathway), was present in the Late
146 Pleistocene just before Brady Soil formation. The predominance of C₃ grasses, along with
147 phytolith evidence for some shrubs or trees (also C₃) continued through the early part of Brady
148 Soil formation, but warm season grasses (C₄ pathway, imparting a distinctive C isotopic
149 signature to soil organic matter) increased later in the development of that soil. Frequent fire
150 during Brady Soil formation is recorded by high black carbon content (**Marín-Spiotta et al.,**
151 **2014**). Isotopic data indicate $\geq 60\%$ C₄ grass biomass through most of the Holocene, although
152 with fluctuations over time.

153 With that background, the key new contributions of this paper are in three areas: a more
154 comprehensive evaluation of the OSL chronology, a test of the potential for extracting
155 paleoenvironmental data from the stable isotopic composition of carbonates in the Peoria Loess-
156 Brady Soil-Bignell Loess sequence, and a high-resolution record from that sequence at a second
157 locality. Although the overall chronology has been well established, it has been based on the
158 tradition of OSL using a single grain size fraction, either the most representative or most
159 abundant in the targeted deposit. It was assumed that different granulometric fractions should
160 yield similar luminescence ages if the necessary corrections for differing interaction with alpha,
161 beta and gamma radiation are taken into account. The question arises, however, as to whether
162 there are substantial differences in the age of quartz grains obtained on different granulometric
163 fractions extracted from loess (see e.g. **Timar-Gabor et al., 2011, 2015, 2017**). The section
164 investigated in this study provides a great opportunity to test whether the usual particle size
165 chosen could have age bias, providing ages on three different particle size classes.

166 Luminescence dating is performed on a suite of grain-sizes of quartz (4-11 μm , 63-90 μm ,
167 90-125 μm) resulting in three sets of luminescence ages for each sample investigated. The
168 purpose of this approach is twofold. Firstly, based on statistic expectations it was suggested
169 decades ago (**Aitken, 1985 Appendix B**) that averaging the dates from the same sedimentary
170 context, although not influencing the systematic errors, can reduce the random uncertainties, thus
171 improving the overall precision on the final age. Typical sources of systematic error usually
172 taken into account during dating procedures are 2% error for beta source calibration, a 3% error
173 on conversion factors, a 15% uncertainty on the estimation cosmic radiation dose, and a 25%
174 uncertainty on the past water content, just to mention some of the most important sources. The
175 total relative random uncertainty for ages obtained on quartz extracted from loess deposits is

176 about 5 % for coarse grain-sizes (grains larger than 63 microns) while for fine grains (4-11 μ m) it
177 is around 3 %. This is due to the significantly larger number of grains used for individual
178 measurements in fine grain dating, the resulting smaller scatter in the values averaged for
179 equivalent dose estimation, or in statistical terms the significantly larger population tested. The
180 final typical combined uncertainty on the age usually amounts to about 10%. Here we explore
181 the potential to improve the precision of the luminescence dating by averaging the ages obtained
182 on multiple grain-sizes taking into consideration the different contributions of systematic and
183 random errors. To our knowledge, except **Constantin et al. (2012)**, the literature lacks such
184 studies.

185 Secondly, luminescence studies on several European loess sites (e.g. **Timar-Gabor et al.,**
186 **2011, 2015; Constantin et al., 2014, 2015**) as well as Chinese loess sites (**Timar-Gabor et al.,**
187 **2017**) reported unexpected age discrepancies between silt sized (4-11 μ m) and fine sand quartz
188 fractions (grains larger than 63 microns), although these differences are generally occurring for
189 ages beyond 40-50 ka. Luminescence dating of Peoria and Bignell loess at Wauneta and other
190 previously studied sites has been based on a single relatively coarse grain size range of quartz
191 (90-150, 90-125, or 30-90 μ m for ages reported by **Mason et al., 2003; Miao et al, 2007a, b;**
192 **and Mason et al., 2008; 35-50 μ m for ages of Roberts et al., 2003**), and more generally, dating
193 of multiple size fractions has not been reported from loess in North America. Thus, this study
194 provides the first opportunity to test whether the luminescence ages of three different particle
195 size classes are in agreement in an important North American loess-paleosol sequence.

196 While previous studies focused on stable isotope composition of organic matter in loess of
197 the Great Plains (**Muhs et al., 1999; Johnson and Willey, 2000; Feggestad et al., 2004; Miao**
198 **et al., 2007a**), in this paper we also for the first time explore the possibility of obtaining detailed
199 Late Pleistocene-Holocene paleoenvironmental records from carbonates in loess and paleosols
200 from the same region, drawing on extensive previous work on pedogenic carbonates in other
201 settings (**Amundson et al., 1988; Cerling et al., 1989; Quade et al., 1989; Breecker et al.,**
202 **2009; Monger et al., 2009**).

203 A final goal of this study was to collect samples for high-resolution analysis of loess
204 sedimentation rate and grain size, magnetic properties influenced by pedogenesis, and stable
205 isotopic data through the Late Pleistocene and Holocene loess of the Great Plains, at an

206 additional site. Such an analysis, combined with intensive OSL and radiocarbon dating, has only
207 been carried out at a single locality, the Wauneta site (Miao et al., 2007a).

208 This paper reports new results from the Enders section (Figure 1), well-suited to provide a
209 well-dated, high-resolution record, with loess-paleosol stratigraphy similar to that observed at the
210 Wauneta site, 12.5 km NNE of Enders. A more comprehensive analysis of OSL ages from three
211 grain size fractions (4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm) and consideration of varying water
212 contents strengthens the chronological basis for interpreting records from both sites. We discuss
213 similarities and differences between the results from Enders and Wauneta sites, distinguishing
214 the regional paleoclimatic signal from effects of local setting, and also compare the loess record
215 of the Pleistocene-Holocene transition from the Great Plains with loess records from Eurasia.

216

217 2. Study site and samples

218 The Enders site (40°23'N, 101°28'W; Fig. 1) is located in southwestern Nebraska, in the
219 central Great Plains of North America. The site remains covered by natural steppe vegetation,
220 dominated by little bluestem (*Schizachyrium scoparius*, a C₄ grass) and sand sage (*Artemisia*
221 *filifolia*, a C₃ shrub). Twelve samples were collected for luminescence dating from the topmost 6
222 meters along two adjacent profiles of the upper and lower parts of the section, with 37 cm of
223 overlap (Supplementary File Figure S1). Paleosols identified visually in the field include the
224 Brady Soil (with a moist Munsell color of 10YR 3/1-3/2) and more weakly developed paleosols
225 (10YR 4/2) in the overlying Holocene loess (Fig. 2). The stratigraphy of loess units and
226 paleosols shown in Figure 2 is similar to that reported from other thick proximal Bignell Loess
227 sections reported from western and central Nebraska (Mason and Kuzila, 2000; Mason et al.,
228 2003; Jacobs and Mason, 2004, Miao et al. 2005). A thick unit of relative unweathered loess
229 (10YR 5/3-5/4) overlies the Brady Soil, and is capped by one of the two most prominent
230 Holocene paleosols. Above this is a sequence of alternating thin, weakly developed buried A
231 horizons and less weathered loess (10YR 4/3-5/3), which varies in detail between sections,
232 capped by the second more prominent Holocene paleosol. The upper 90 cm is light-colored loess
233 (10YR 5/3) with varying degrees of very weak pedogenesis; a similar unit is present in almost all
234 reported Holocene loess sections of the region (Mason and Kuzila, 2000; Mason et al., 2003;
235 Jacobs and Mason, 2004, Miao et al. 2005; Miao et al. 2007a).

236

237 **3. Methods and instrumentation**

238 Determinations of particle size, magnetic susceptibility, and stable C and O isotope
239 analyses were made on 350 sediment samples collected at 2 cm resolution from carefully cleaned
240 outcrop walls (Supplementary File **Figure S1**).

241 **3.1. Magnetic susceptibility**

242 The volumetric magnetic susceptibility was measured at frequencies of 300 Hz (χ_{lf}) and
243 3000 Hz (χ_{hf}) in a static field of 300 mA/m using a Magnon International VSMF
244 (sensitivity $\sim 10^{-7}$ SI). All data were corrected for drift and for the effect of holder and sampling
245 boxes (weak diamagnetism) and normalized to mass. Frequency dependence of magnetic
246 susceptibility (χ_{fd}) was expressed as a mass-specific loss of susceptibility $\chi_{fd} = ((\chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf}) / \chi_{lf}) * 100$
247 (**Dearing et al., 1996**).

248 **3.2. Grain size**

249 Grain-size measurements were performed by immersing dry sample material in 400 mL
250 deionized water, adding 10 mL 50 g L⁻¹ Na-metaphosphate dispersant solution, and sonicating
251 for 6 min prior to analysis in a Malvern Mastersizer 2000MU laser diffraction particle size
252 analyzer. Organic matter and carbonates were not removed prior to analysis. Previous work
253 (**Mason et al., 2007**) and experiments for this study showed that for Nebraska loess these
254 treatments do not increase the measured clay and fine silt contents relative to what is released by
255 sonication plus chemical dispersion; thus organic matter ($\leq 1\%$ at Wauneta, **Miao et al., 2007a**)
256 and carbonates ($< 3\%$ at Wauneta, J. Mason, unpublished data) bind aggregates only weakly and
257 do not limit clay dispersion. In fact, removal of organic matter and carbonates in some cases
258 unexpectedly causes significant reductions in finer fractions measured by laser diffraction (see
259 **Mason et al., 2011** for more discussion). For comparison, samples at 2 cm intervals from a core
260 at Wauneta were reanalyzed by identical methods in the same instrument, since methods used
261 earlier by **Miao et al. (2007a)** were slightly different.

262 **3.3. Stable carbon isotope analysis**

263 The use of carbon and oxygen isotopic compositions of pedogenic carbonates to
264 reconstruct change in vegetation composition (C_3 vs. C_4), temperature, and/or other
265 environmental variables is well-established, based on well-developed theory and observations of
266 modern soils that have also revealed complexities in interpretation (**Amundson et al., 1988**;
267 **Cerling et al., 1989**; **Quade et al., 1989**; **Breecker et al., 2009**; **Monger et al., 2009**).

268 Carbonates are present through all or much of the Brady Soil and Bignell Loess, mainly evident
269 macroscopically as fine mycelia suggesting in *situ* pedogenic formation. Unfortunately, it has not
270 been possible to separate clearly pedogenic carbonate features from the soil matrix, which may
271 contain some inherited (detrital) carbonates. Peoria Loess in western Nebraska contains 0-4%
272 carbonate (Muhs et al, 2008; Yang et al., 2017), some probably inherited from pedogenic or
273 diagenetic carbonates in the continental Cenozoic source rocks. A significant content of marine
274 carbonates is less likely given the loess provenance.

275 With that background, the stable carbon and oxygen isotopic compositions of bulk
276 carbonate in the Enders section were analyzed as a pilot study to assess the potential for
277 paleoenvironmental reconstruction, recognizing that interpretation may be complicated because of
278 the possible inclusion of inherited carbonate. Loess samples were crushed and mixed in an agate
279 mortar, turning them into a fine powder, and 0.1 g of each ground sample was reacted with 100%
280 phosphoric acid (1 mL H₃PO₄) to release CO₂.

281 The determination of the oxygen and carbon isotopic ratios extracted from CO₂ was
282 performed using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Delta V Advantage, Thermo Fisher
283 Scientific, Germany) coupled with dual inlet system.

284 Values of ¹³C/¹²C and ¹⁸O/¹⁶O are denoted in delta versus Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (V-
285 PDB) international standard, according to the equation (Brand et al., 2014):

286
$$\delta^i X (\text{‰}) = 1000 \left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}}} - 1 \right)$$

287 where *i* is the mass number of the heavier isotope of the element X (e.g. ¹³C, ¹⁸O), *R_{sample}* is the
288 isotope number ratio of a sample (for example, ¹³C/¹²C), and *R_{standard}* is that of the VPDB
289 standard. The isotope ratio mass-spectrometer was calibrated against the International Atomic
290 Energy Agency (IAEA) reference material IAEA-CO-1 marble (δ¹³C = +2.492 ‰, δ¹⁸O = -
291 2.4‰). Each sample was analyzed in duplicate and the limit of uncertainty was ± 0.2 ‰ for both
292 isotopes.

293

294 3.4. OSL dating

295 3.4.1. Sampling and sample preparation

296 Twelve samples were collected for luminescence dating from Enders section. The sampling
297 was performed by hammering stainless steel cylinders perpendicularly onto two freshly cleaned

298 vertical exposures. At the Luminescence Laboratory at Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca,
299 Romania, the material at each end of the cylinders was extracted for high-resolution gamma
300 spectrometry measurements and water content estimations. The core sediment for each tube was
301 processed to extract fine (4-11 µm) and coarse (63-90 µm and 90-125 µm) quartz under low-
302 intensity red light conditions in the laboratory. In order to isolate different grain sizes of pure
303 quartz (4-11 µm, 63-90 µm and 90-125 µm), the samples were first treated with hydrochloric
304 acid (HCl, concentration of 35%) for carbonate removal and with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂,
305 concentration of 30%) for organic matter removal.

306 The coarse grain fractions (63-90 and 90-125 µm) were separated through dry sieving.
307 Since this fraction consisted in undifferentiated mixture of polyminerals including quartz,
308 feldspars and heavy minerals, a two steps density separation centrifugation using heavy liquids
309 was performed in order to extract coarse quartz grains. The heavy liquid solution contained
310 sodium metatungstate Na₆[H₂W₁₂O₄₀] x H₂O and distilled water. First the quartz (density 2.65 -
311 2.66 g/cm³) and plagioclase grains were separated from the lighter minerals (such as K-feldspars)
312 by centrifugation in a 2.62 g/cm³ heavy liquid solution. The second step employed a 2.75 g/cm³
313 heavy liquid solution, in which the quartz and plagioclase feldspars were isolated from the heavy
314 minerals such as zircons and apatite. The treatment with HF (40% concentration) for 40 minutes
315 performed in order to isolate the quartz grains from the plagioclase feldspar and to discard the
316 exterior layer of the quartz grain which has been penetrated by alpha radiation. A rinse with
317 hydrochloric acid (10% concentration) for 60 minutes removed the fluorides that precipitated
318 following the HF attack. For measurement, coarse quartz grains (63-90 and 90-125 µm) were
319 then mounted on stainless steel disks with silicon oil as adhesive.

320 The polymineral fine fraction (4-11 µm) was separated by settling in Atterberg cylinders
321 and was etched with 35% hexafluorosilicic acid (H₂SiF₆) for 10 days in order to enrich the quartz
322 extracts. The 4-11 µm quartz grains were mounted on aluminium disks from a suspension in
323 acetone (2 mg/ml).

324

325 **3.4.2. Equivalent dose determination**

326 Measurements were carried out using standard and automated Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 readers
327 equipped with classic or automated detection and stimulation head (DASH) (Lapp et al., 2015).
328 Signals were detected by EMI 9235QA and PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 photomultiplier tubes

329 (Thomsen, 2006). Irradiation was performed using the incorporated ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y beta source,
330 calibrated using gamma irradiated calibration quartz produced by Risø National Laboratory,
331 Denmark (Hansen et al., 2015). The dose rates of the two readers used for the coarse (63-90 and
332 90-125 μm) quartz grains deposited on stainless steel disks were 0.088 Gy/s and 0.129 Gy/s,
333 respectively, while for the fine grains mounted on aluminium disks and measured on the first of
334 the two above mentioned readers the dose rate was 0.078 Gy/s at the time of measurement.

335 OSL investigations were carried out using the single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR)
336 protocol for the fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 and 90-125 μm) fractions (Murray and
337 Wintle, 2000; 2003). Luminescence signals were stimulated with blue light emitting diodes for
338 40 s at 125°C, while the signals were recorded through a 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340 UV filter.
339 The net CW-OSL signal was evaluated from the first 0.308 s of the decay curve with an early
340 background subtraction assessed from the 1.69-2.30 s interval (Cunningham and Wallinga,
341 2010). Unless otherwise stated, a preheat of 220°C for 10 s and a cutheat of 180°C were
342 employed throughout the SAR protocol. The OSL response to a fixed test dose of 17 Gy was
343 used throughout the whole set of measurements to correct for sensitivity changes. A high-
344 temperature bleach was performed by stimulation with blue LEDs for 40 s at 280°C at the end of
345 each test dose signal measurement (Murray and Wintle, 2003).

346 The suitability of these samples for D_e determination using the SAR protocol was tested in
347 terms of recycling, infrared (IR) depletion and recuperation tests. The purity of the quartz
348 extracts was evaluated using OSL IR depletion tests (Duller, 2003) on all aliquots measured.
349 OSL IR depletion and recycling ratios within a maximum deviation of 10% from unity
350 constituted the acceptance criteria along a recuperation signal amounting to less than 2% of the
351 natural signal. None of the investigated aliquots have been rejected due to poor recycling, IR
352 depletion or recuperation values.

353 We carried out investigations on three independent grain sizes of quartz (4-11 μm , 63-90
354 μm and 90-125 μm) for two reasons. First, if ages are found to be in good agreement this is an
355 argument for their accuracy. Secondly, a set of three ages that are concordant allows for
356 calculation of a weighted average age that better reflects the age of deposition and for which the
357 random error is reduced.

358

359 3.4.3. Dosimetry

360 The specific activities of radionuclides were measured by means of high resolution gamma
361 spectrometry. Measurements were performed using a hyperpure germanium well detector with a
362 volume of 120 cm³, full width at half maximum (FWHM) at 122 keV of 1.40 KeV and a full
363 width at half maximum (FWHM) at 1332 KeV of 2.30 KeV. Dose rates were derived
364 considering secular equilibrium in the ²³⁸U chain, based on the conversion factors reported by
365 **Adamiec and Aitken (1998)**. The beta attenuation and etching factors for 63-90 μm and 90-125
366 μm fractions were assumed to be 0.94 ± 0.05 and 0.92 ± 0.05 , respectively (**Mejdahl, 1979**). For
367 the fine quartz fraction, an alpha efficiency factor of 0.04 ± 0.02 was assumed to account for the
368 lower efficiency of alpha radiation in inducing luminescence (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). Water content
369 estimation was based on the difference between the raw and the oven-dried weight of material
370 with a relative error of 25%. An internal dose rate of 0.01 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered
371 (**Vandenberghé et al., 2008**). The cosmic ray component of the dose rate was calculated using
372 the equations published by **Prescott and Huton (1994)**. The values for radionuclide
373 concentrations as well as the total dose rates for these samples are given in **Table 1**.

374

375 **4. Results**

376 **4.1. Grain size, magnetic susceptibility, and stable isotope results**

377 Grain size data (**Figure 3**) indicate a much higher content of the >63 μm fraction (20-38%)
378 than in typical loess of other regions, also observed at the Wauneta site (**Miao et al., 2007a**) and
379 indicating short-distance transport in suspension at a low height above ground (**Pye, 1987, p. 50-**
380 **51**). The >63 μm fraction is least in the Brady Soil and is somewhat lower in the upper
381 prominent Holocene paleosol (~130-90 cm) than in the rest of the Bignell Loess. There is a
382 proportional increase in the fine <16 μm fraction in both of those soils and the <2 μm fraction
383 also increases in the Brady Soil. At the Wauneta site, the <16 μm fraction is relatively high in the
384 Brady Soil and both major Holocene paleosols, although with significant variation within each
385 paleosol.

386 The most interesting aspect of the grain size profile involves variation just above and
387 within the Brady Soil (**Figure 3**). A spike of fine material, more pronounced for the <2 μm
388 fraction μm than for the <16 μm fraction at Enders, occurs just above the Brady Soil (peak 1 in
389 Figure 4), while a second peak, much more distinct for the <16 μm fraction than for the <2 μm
390 fraction, falls within the upper Brady Soil A horizon (peak 2). A third, especially prominent peak

391 of both $<2 \mu\text{m}$ and $<16 \mu\text{m}$ fractions marks the Brady Soil Bk horizon (peak 3). Three peaks of
392 fine material at similar stratigraphic positions occur in the Wauneta site grain size profile. At
393 both sites, each of these peaks are defined by three or more samples.

394 The low-frequency magnetic susceptibility (χ_{lf}) varies between $122 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$ and $200 \cdot 10^{-8}$
395 m^3/kg (**Figure 4**). χ_{lf} is slightly elevated within the Brady Soil, compared to the underlying
396 Peoria Loess and the relatively unweathered Bignell Loess just above it, with some variation
397 among Brady Soil horizons. More distinct χ_{lf} peaks correspond loosely to the two more
398 prominent Holocene buried soils, with the upper peak extending into the light-colored loess in
399 the upper 90 cm of the section. χ_{fd} shows minor enhancement in the Brady Soil but not in the
400 Holocene paleosols. All of these results are similar to those obtained at the Wauneta site (**Figure**
401 **4 of Miao et al., 2007a**), although the χ_{lf} and χ_{fd} profiles differ in detail between these sites.

402 Comparison of C isotopic compositions of bulk carbonate from Enders and organic matter
403 from Wauneta suggests that the carbonates analysed at Enders are predominantly pedogenic,
404 formed *in situ*, and record vegetation change (C_4 vs. C_3 plants) (**Figure 5**). In both profiles of
405 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, the Peoria Loess is characterized by particularly low values, with a substantial increase
406 within the Brady Soil, a peak around the depth of the prominent paleosol in the middle of the
407 Bignell Loess, and low-high-low fluctuations from there to the ground surface. At Wauneta,
408 these fluctuations record changing proportions of C_3 and C_4 biomass; other effects are likely to
409 be minor (**Feggestad et al., 2004**). Comparing corresponding peaks and troughs, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values
410 of carbonate at Enders are consistently about 11-13‰ higher than those of organic matter at
411 Wauneta. This is somewhat lower than the offset of ca. 15‰ expected between pedogenic
412 carbonate and organic matter in the same soil, if the carbonate formed below about 50 cm depth,
413 where soil CO_2 is dominated by root and microbial respiration with an isotopic composition
414 close to that of soil organic matter (**Quade et al., 1989; Cerling and Quade, 1993**). The
415 discrepancy could have a variety of explanations, including lower C_4 biomass at Enders (e.g.
416 more shrubs, less grass) than at Wauneta or the presence of some inherited pedogenic carbonates
417 formed in C_3 -dominated environments and thus having lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$; seasonality of carbonate
418 precipitation also affects the resulting $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (**Breecker et al., 2009**). Interestingly, corresponding
419 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ peaks tend to be offset to greater stratigraphic depths in the carbonate profile from Enders
420 than in the organic matter profile from Wauneta. The uppermost and middle peaks of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ are
421 just above the two prominent Holocene paleosols at Wauneta, but within them at Enders, and the

422 sharp rise in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from Peoria Loess into the Brady Soil is somewhat deeper at Enders relative to
423 Brady Soil horizons. This may be explained by carbonate formation somewhat below the active
424 root zone, which rose with ongoing loess accumulation, so the carbonate formed
425 contemporaneously with organic matter at a somewhat shallower depth. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile at
426 Enders tracks fairly closely with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ profile (**Figure 5**). The values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ are especially
427 low in the Late Pleistocene part of the section (upper Peoria Loess), increasing along with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
428 through the Brady Soil, with two more zones of low values in the late Holocene. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of
429 pedogenic carbonate varies with that of local meteoric water, though potentially shifted by
430 evaporation (**Cerling and Quade, 1993**). Low $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the Late Pleistocene may be attributable
431 to more depleted meteoric water in the glacial climate of that time; however, the similarly low
432 values in the late Holocene are difficult to explain at this point. The abrupt shift of both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and
433 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of carbonate at Enders to very negative values near the ground surface cannot be explained
434 at this time.

435

436 **4.2. Luminescence properties and equivalent doses**

437 The equivalent doses were determined by projecting the sensitivity corrected natural OSL
438 signal onto the dose response curve constructed in each case. Representative SAR growth curves
439 for a single aliquot of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm and 90-125 μm) grained quartz from
440 END 1.2 and END 1.10 samples are given in **Figure 6**. The OSL signals displayed a rapid decay
441 during optical stimulation. The shapes of the OSL decay curves for this sample are almost
442 identical to that obtained for the calibration quartz supplied by the Risø National Laboratory (see
443 the inset to **Figure 6**).

444 For each investigated sample, between 10 and 20 replicate measurements of the equivalent
445 dose were performed. Results of equivalent dose measurements and standard SAR performance
446 tests are presented in Supplementary File **Table S1**.

447 Dose recovery tests (**Murray and Wintle, 2003**) were conducted to investigate the
448 reliability of the equivalent doses obtained by applying the SAR protocol on fine (4-11 μm) and
449 coarse (63-90 μm) quartz grains from samples END 1.4, END 1.6, END 1.8, END 1.10 and END
450 1.12. During this test, the aliquots were stimulated twice for 250 s at room temperature using the
451 blue LEDs with a 10 ka pause inserted between the stimulation. The aliquots were then irradiated
452 with known beta doses chosen to be equal to the estimated equivalent dose. A preheat of a 220

453 °C for 10 s in combination with a test dose ramp heating to 180 °C (cutheat) were used in the
454 SAR protocol. As seen in Supplementary File **Fig. S2**, very good recovery to given dose ratios
455 were obtained in all cases, indicating that the laboratory doses given prior to any heat treatment
456 are measured with accuracy using the SAR protocol.

457 The variation in D_e as a function of preheat temperature in combination with a 180 °C
458 cutheat was also investigated. Aliquots of fine and coarse quartz from sample END 1.8 were
459 separated in groups of five, each corresponding to a temperature point (180°C, 200°C, 220°C,
460 240°C, 260°C, 280°C). As shown in Supplementary File **Fig. S3**, the plateau observed validates
461 the choice of a 220°C preheat temperature.

462 The D_e distribution obtained for 58 single aliquots from the END 1.8 (63-90 μm) sample
463 taken from the Brady Soil is presented in Supplementary File **Fig. S4 and Fig. S5**, using both a
464 histogram and a radial plot. In radial plot (**Galbraith, 1999**) each result is plotted against the
465 relative standard error. All aliquots show relative standard errors of <4%. In this graph all points
466 having the same dose estimate lie on a straight line connecting the origin on the y-axis and the
467 dose value on the circular scale to the right. The use of the standardised estimate for the y axis
468 allows the $\pm 2\sigma$ band to be plotted (the shaded band in Supplementary File **Fig. S5**). The
469 overdispersion value is 7.2 ± 0.8 and the vast majority of D_e values are spread randomly around
470 a central value (Supplementary File **Fig. S5**). Our sample behavior, although collected from a
471 soil unit, is typical of those that are known or are thought to have been well-bleached prior to
472 burial and remained undisturbed since burial (**Galbraith and Roberts, 2012**), thus increasing the
473 confidence in the obtained results.

474

475 **4.3. OSL ages**

476 Luminescence age determination, more specifically the annual dose determination,
477 implies estimation of a “fixed” value of the moisture content in each sample that would reflect
478 the average water content over the burial period, based on which the correction for its attenuation
479 effects is performed. Given the difficulty of reconstructing the water content in loess-paleosol
480 deposits over the time since deposition one can assume water content based on “as found” values
481 and known paleoclimatic conditions for the investigated area to which a large uncertainty (25-50
482 % relative error) is associated. In order to evaluate the effect of a varying moisture content
483 during burial on the luminescence ages we have calculated the ages using “as found” as well as

484 averaged moisture contents of $5 \pm 1.3 \%$ and $10 \pm 2.5 \%$ for all samples (Supplementary File
485 **Table S2**). The OSL ages display an increase with greater water content by about 5% and still
486 agree within error limits. Sampling from an outcrop may have resulted in low “as found”
487 moisture contents, but the Bignell Loess is often quite dry even when sampled in cores, and
488 during the Holocene the climate was frequently drier than at present (**Miao et al., 2007b**);
489 therefore the error margins of the ages based on “as found” moisture values with a 25% relative
490 error are likely to be sufficiently high to incorporate the uncertainties of long-term fluctuations in
491 moisture. Future work on modeling hydrology of the loess-paleosol sequence under various
492 climatic scenarios may refine this approach.

493 Within uncertainties, optical ages are in agreement for all grain sizes of quartz (4-11 μm ,
494 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm) except for the case of END 1.6 90-125 μm quartz age which we
495 consider to be an outlier (see **Table 1**). Uncertainties on the individual ages were calculated
496 based on the error assessment system described by **Aitken and Aldred (1972)** and **Aitken**
497 **(1976)**. The systematic errors on the individual ages for the fine grains amount to a maximum of
498 8% while for coarse grains systematic errors amounted to a maximum of 6%, respectively. The
499 systematic error is particularly related to our estimates of the uncertainties associated with the
500 time-averaged water content, alpha efficiency and beta attenuation factors. The random error
501 represents a measure of the internal consistency of the optical ages and extended to 9% for the
502 coarse grains. In the case of the fine grains the random error does not exceed 6%.

503 The weighted average fine and coarse quartz ages are reported in the last column of **Table**
504 **1** and were calculated following **Aitken (1985) Appendix B**. The overall error in the age is
505 quantified as the square root of the sum of the squares (quadrature) of total random and
506 systematic uncertainties, respectively.

507

508 **5. Discussion**

509 **5.1. Implications for high-resolution paleoclimatic records from the Brady Soil and Bignell** 510 **Loess.**

511 The new OSL chronology and other data from the Enders section provide important new
512 support for interpretation of Great Plains loess as a high-resolution paleoclimatic record,
513 especially for the Pleistocene-Holocene transition and the Holocene. Comparison of high-
514 resolution grain size profiles between the Enders and Wauneta sites, in particular, suggests that

515 fine-scale variation through the Brady Soil may provide important new information on details of
516 the last glacial-interglacial transition in central North America. Local effects are revealed mainly
517 by minor variations in stratigraphy.

518 The application of typical intrinsic rigor tests of the OSL dating method as well as the use
519 of three grain size fractions of quartz leads to high confidence in the OSL ages obtained from the
520 Enders section. Furthermore, the new OSL dating results (**Figure 2, Table 1**) are largely
521 consistent with earlier OSL and ^{14}C dating in similar stratigraphic positions at Wauneta and other
522 sites. The weighted average ages of the two samples in upper Peoria Loess just below the Brady
523 Soil Bkb horizon are 14.0 ± 0.9 ka (649 cm) and 13.1 ± 0.8 ka (601 cm), consistent with other
524 results from the central Great Plains (**Roberts et al., 2003; Mason et al., 2008**). The weighted
525 OSL ages obtained from the lowermost Brady Soil Bkb horizon and from just above the Brady
526 Soil Akb horizon are 12.7 ± 0.8 ka and 9.5 ± 0.6 ka, respectively, in agreement with the
527 previously published OSL and ^{14}C chronologies (**Johnson and Willey, 2000; Mason et al.,**
528 **2008; Miao et al., 2005; 2007a**).

529 Within the Bignell Loess, OSL dating at other sites indicated that the thick, relatively
530 unweathered loess above the Brady soil accumulated rapidly between about 10 ka and just after
531 6.5 ka, before a mid-Holocene slowdown in loess accumulation led to formation of a distinct soil
532 (**Miao et al., 2005**). The ages from Enders suggest rapid accumulation was not replaced by soil
533 formation until after 6.2 ± 0.4 ka which is in agreement with previous work. Above the mid-
534 Holocene soil, data from both loess sections and nearby sand dunes indicate an interval of greater
535 eolian activity between ~ 4.5 and 2.3 ka, with two peaks at about 3.8 and 2.5 ka, separated by a
536 weak soil in thick loess sections but not clearly distinguishable in the dunes (**Miao et al.,**
537 **2007b**). At Enders the age of 3.1 ± 0.2 ka (307 cm) obtained in loess is younger than ages of 4.0-
538 3.7 ka at the same stratigraphic position elsewhere, but the ages of 2.4 ± 0.2 ka (207 cm) and $2.2 \pm$
539 0.2 ka (147 cm) obtained in loess are close to stratigraphically equivalent ages of 2.6-2.3 ka
540 elsewhere (**Miao et al., 2007b**). The entire interval encompassing all these ages varies
541 considerably in stratigraphic and pedologic detail between sites, so the timing of intervals of
542 loess sedimentation may have varied spatially. The age of 0.6 ± 0.0 ka (77 cm) from the light-
543 colored loess above the upper Holocene paleosol at Enders is consistent with ages from this
544 stratigraphic interval at other sites (**Miao et al., 2007b**). More rapid loess accumulation recorded
545 by this uppermost unit apparently began during the period of frequent widespread droughts

546 associated with the Medieval Climate Anomaly (**Cook et al., 2004**), but continued well after it in
547 at least some areas.

548 The Brady Soil is marked by finer grain size at both Enders and Wauneta sites, as are the
549 two most distinct Holocene paleosols, at least in terms of the <16 μm fraction. Importantly,
550 however, the fine-grained particle content is not uniformly high in the Brady Soil. Instead, three
551 peaks of fine material, one just above the Brady Soil Akb horizon, one in the upper Akb horizon,
552 and one in the Bkb horizon, can be correlated between the two sites (**Figure 3**). The relative
553 magnitude and other details of these peaks vary between the two sections, but not their position
554 relative to the paleosol horizons.

555 It is unlikely that weathering after deposition could explain the formation of the similar fine
556 structure of the grain size profile through the Brady Soil at both of these sites, given the short
557 time period involved and the steppe environment present throughout Brady Soil formation
558 (**Woodburn et al., 2017**). Pedogenic translocation of fine silt and clay is also an unlikely
559 explanation, given that OSL ages from the finest fraction are similar to those from the coarsest
560 fraction for samples within the Brady Soil at Enders. Furthermore, although mammal and insect
561 burrows are common in the Brady Soil (**Jacobs and Mason, 2004**), the typical depth scale of
562 thorough mixing by bioturbation must be fairly limited, or the three correlative fine-grained
563 peaks would not be preserved. Thus, the OSL ages from within the Brady Soil primarily reflect
564 time of deposition of loess of different grain-size characteristics that slowly accumulated as the
565 soil formed (**Mason et al., 2008**) rather than deep, thorough mixing by bioturbation.

566 Given that interpretation of slow, ongoing accumulation, we interpret the variation in fine-
567 grained content as the result of significant changes in the conditions affecting the emission,
568 transport, and/or deposition of dust (**Újvári et al., 2016**) during the period of Brady Soil
569 formation. Changes in the wind speed distribution are one obvious explanation; another
570 possibility is a shift toward lower dust emission from closer to more distant parts of the primary
571 source area, increasing the relative contribution of finer dust from more distant sources. An
572 intriguing alternative is that the fine-grained peaks correspond to changes in precipitation,
573 affecting the proportions of wet and dry deposition. The potential effects of greater rainfall on
574 loess grain size are complex. Within the size range of loess, rainfall more efficiently removes
575 larger particles from an atmospheric dust plume (**Újvári et al., 2016**); however, this could
576 presumably make dust deposited farther downwind more fine-grained. Mapping the spatial

577 pattern of grain-size variation within and just above the Brady Soil across the central Great
578 Plains, combined with insight from process studies of wet and dry deposition, could allow
579 evaluation of a link to precipitation changes during the last deglaciation in this region. The OSL
580 chronology at Enders does not allow definite assignment of the fine-grained peaks to more
581 widely recognized stages of the last deglaciation. The deepest peak could fall just before or in the
582 early part of the Younger Dryas (Alley et al., 1993; Alley, 2000) and the upper two apparently
583 fall after the end of the Younger Dryas.

584 Comparison of the magnetic measurements at the Enders and Wauneta sites suggests that
585 these properties are influenced by both regional climatic change and local effects. Greater χ_{lf}
586 generally occurs within Holocene paleosols at both sites, consistent with pedogenic
587 enhancement, although lower χ_{lf} in the Brady Soil at both sites is difficult to explain at this point.
588 The χ_{fd} profiles differ between the two sites however, with little evidence of pedogenic effects at
589 Wauneta. Interpretation of the isotopic records from Enders is difficult because of the potential
590 inclusion of inherited carbonate. However, the similarity in temporal patterns between the Enders
591 carbonate-based record and the $\delta^{13}C$ profile from organic matter at the Wauneta site suggests that
592 the carbonate at Enders may be largely pedogenic, and that it records similar Late Pleistocene-
593 Holocene vegetation change as at Wauneta. That observation implies that isotopic analysis of
594 carbonates in Brady Soil-Bignell Loess sections could potentially provide a valuable new source
595 of paleoenvironmental information, especially through the additional insight provided by O
596 isotopic composition and possibly clumped isotope methods (Eiler, 2007). Realizing this
597 potential will be dependent on developing methods to isolate pure pedogenic carbonate (or
598 showing that inherited carbonate is insignificant) and determining the time of carbonate
599 precipitation relative to loess deposition and organic matter accumulation.

600 The greatest difference between the Enders and Wauneta sections is in the relative
601 thickness of the relatively unweathered loess between the Brady Soil and the lower prominent
602 Holocene soil. At Enders this loess represents just under 30% of the total Bignell Loess
603 thickness, but in the thickest Wauneta section (Figure 2 of Miao et al., 2007) the proportion is
604 almost 50%. At some other thick Bignell Loess sections the proportion is even greater (e.g. New
605 Wauneta Roadcut, Miao et al., 2005). Stratigraphic details and thickness of paleosols and loess
606 units in the late Holocene loess also vary among sections that have been studied, including

607 Enders. These local differences could reflect spatially varying availability of wind-erodible
608 sediment at nearby sources in various parts of the Holocene.

609

610 **5.2. Contrast with Eurasian loess records of the last glacial-interglacial transition and** 611 **Holocene.**

612 The new chronology presented here supports earlier interpretations that the most significant
613 Late Pleistocene to Holocene interval of soil formation, producing the Brady Soil, spanned the
614 Pleistocene-Holocene boundary. While the Brady Soil initially resembles a simple, monogenetic
615 soil profile, it formed through multiple large shifts in the grain size of slowly accumulating loess,
616 probably recording climatic episodes during the glacial-interglacial transition. In Eurasian loess
617 records, from the Danubian loess of southeastern Europe to the Chinese Loess Plateau, soil
618 formation began later than in the central Great Plains and continued through all or much of the
619 Holocene (**Stevens et al., 2011; Dong et al., 2015; Marković et al., 2014; 2018; Constantin et**
620 **al., 2019**). In China, however, the Holocene soil S0 in some sections closer to dry source regions
621 of the loess represents a complex sequence of loess accumulation and pedogenesis, relatively
622 similar to the Brady Soil. Finally most Chinese S0 profiles are buried by latest Holocene loess
623 (L0) (e.g. Baicaoyuan, Shiguanzhi, Yuanbao sections) (**Lai and Wintle, 2006; Stevens et al.,**
624 **2006; Zhao et al., 2013**). These stratigraphic differences can be explained by a combination of
625 regional climatic change reducing dust emission earlier in the central Great Plains, and location
626 of abundant source material for the Great Plains loess in a setting that was highly sensitive to
627 relatively minor Holocene climatic shifts.

628

629 **6. Conclusions**

630 Optically stimulated luminescence dating of 4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz has
631 been reported for the Enders section located in southwestern Nebraska, midcontinental North
632 America that includes well-preserved Peoria Loess, Brady Soil and Bignell Loess units. Based
633 on the successful results of typical intrinsic rigor tests of the SAR protocol and agreement
634 between the three grain size fractions of quartz, we are fully confident that the obtained OSL
635 ages are accurate. By averaging the three sets of ages available for each sample, the overall error
636 has been reduced to around 4-6%, demonstrating the potential of improving the precision of
637 luminescence dating.

638 The OSL ages indicate that Peoria Loess deposition ended around 13-14 ka. The
639 termination of Peoria Loess deposition is marked by the Brady Soil, bracketed here by OSL ages
640 of 12.7 ± 0.8 ka to 9.5 ± 0.6 ka. We further confirm that Bignell Loess accumulated episodically
641 throughout the Holocene, starting from around 9.5 ka. The new OSL dating results for Enders
642 section are largely consistent with earlier OSL and ^{14}C dating in similar stratigraphic positions at
643 Wauneta and other sites, adding confidence to the regional loess chronology. The high-resolution
644 grain size profile from Enders shares many features with similar data from the previously studied
645 Wauneta site, suggesting that fine-scale variation through the Brady Soil may provide important
646 new information on details of the last glacial-interglacial transition in central North America.
647 The similarity in temporal patterns between the Enders carbonate-based record and the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
648 profile from organic matter at the Wauneta site suggests that the carbonate at Enders may be
649 largely pedogenic, and that it records similar Late Pleistocene-Holocene vegetation change as at
650 Wauneta. However, the interpretation of the isotopic records from Enders is difficult because of
651 the potential inclusion of inherited carbonate.

652 Here we have shown that with adequate age control and high-resolution sampling, loess
653 sections in the central Great Plains can provide a regionally coherent record of the Pleistocene-
654 Holocene transition and Holocene climatic change, not just at the orbital to millennial-scale
655 resolution of visible paleosols and loess units but at a finer millennial to centennial timescale.
656 That goal is important not only for understanding the paleoclimatic history of the Great Plains
657 region, but also for comparison with the loess record of Eurasia. High-resolution analyses of
658 grain size, color, stable carbon isotopic composition of organic matter (e.g. **Johnson and Willey,**
659 **2000; Miao et al., 2007a**) and of pedogenic carbonate if possible, and magnetic properties,
660 combined with OSL and radiocarbon dating should be carried out at additional loess sections
661 across the central Great Plains. The results should indicate the regional occurrence and spatial
662 patterns of fine-scale features, like the peaks of fine-grained material identified within and just
663 above the Brady Soil in this study, providing evidence on the aeolian and pedogenic processes
664 that produced them and their paleoclimatic significance. With that additional background, these
665 features can potentially help resolve details of climatic evolution through the last deglaciation in
666 a part of the North American midcontinent where other records are scarce.

667

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678

679 **References**

- 680 1. Adamiec, G., Aitken, M.J., 1998. Dose-rate conversion factors: update. *Ancient TL* 16,
681 37-50.
- 682 2. Aitken, M.J., 1976. Thermoluminescent age evaluation and assessment of error limits:
683 revised system. *Archaeometry* 18, 233-238. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.1976.tb00168.x)
684 [4754.1976.tb00168.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.1976.tb00168.x).
- 685 3. Aitken, M.J., 1985. Thermoluminescence dating. Academic Press, London, 153 pp.
- 686 4. Aitken, M.J., Alldred, J.C., 1972. The assessment of error limits in thermoluminescent
687 dating. *Archaeometry* 14, 257-267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.1972.tb00068.x>.
- 688 5. Aleinikoff, J.N., Muhs, D.R., Bettis, E.A., Johnson, W.C., Fanning, C.M., Benton, R.,
689 2008. Isotopic evidence for the diversity of late Quaternary loess in Nebraska:
690 Glaciogenic and nonglaciogenic sources. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 120, 1362-1377.
691 <https://doi.org/10.1130/B26222.1>.
- 692 6. Alley, R.B., 2000. The Younger Dryas cold interval as viewed from central Greenland.
693 *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 19, 213-226. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(99\)00062-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(99)00062-1).
- 694 7. Alley, R.B., Meese, D.A., Shuman, C.A., Gow, A.J., Taylor, K.C., Grootes, P.M., White,
695 J.W. C., Ram, M., Waddington, E.D., Mayewski, P.A., Zielinski, G.A., 1993. Abrupt
696 increase in Greenland snow accumulation at the end of the Younger Dryas event. *Nature*
697 362: 527-529. <https://doi.org/10.1038/362527a0>.
- 698 8. Amundson, R.G., Chadwick, O.A., Sowers, J.M., Doner, H.E., 1988. Relationship
699 between climate and vegetation and the stable isotope chemistry of soils in the eastern

- 700 Mojave Desert, Nevada. *Quat. Res.* 29, 245-254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/0033->
701 5894(88)90033-6.
- 702 9. Brand, W.A., Coplen, T.B., Vogl, J., Rosner, M., Prohaska, T., 2014. Assessment of
703 international reference materials for isotope-ratio analysis. IUPAC technical report.
704 *Pure Appl. Chem.* 86, 425–467. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2013-1023>.
- 705 10. Breecker, D.O., Sharp, Z.D., McFadden, L.D., 2009. Seasonal bias in the formation and
706 stable isotopic composition of pedogenic carbonate in modern soils from central New
707 Mexico, USA. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 121, 630-640. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1130/B26413.1>.
- 708 11. Cerling, T.E., Quade, J., Wang, Y., Bowman, J.R. 1989. Carbon isotopes in soils and
709 paleosols as ecology and paleoecology indicators. *Nature* 341, 138-139.
710 <https://doi.org/10.1038/341138a0>.
- 711 12. Constantin, D., Timar-Gabor, A., Veres, D., Begy, R., Cosma, C., 2012. SAR-OSL dating
712 of quartz of different grain sizes extracted from a loess section in southern Romania
713 embedding the Campanian Ignimbrite/Y5 tephra layer, *Quat. Geochronol.* 10, 81-86.
714 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2012.01.012>
- 715 13. Constantin, D., Begy, R., Vasiliniuc, S., Panaiotu, C., Necula, C., Codrea, V., Timar-
716 Gabor, A., 2014. High resolution OSL dating of the Costine ti section Romania using
717 fine and coarse quartz. *Quat. Int.* 334-335, 20-29.
718 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2013.06.016>
- 719 14. Constantin, D., Camenita, A., Panaiotu, C., Necula, C., Codrea, V., Timar-Gabor, A.,
720 2015. Fine and coarse-quartz SAR-OSL dating of Last Glacial loess in Southern
721 Romania. *Quat. Int.* 357, 33-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.07.052>
- 722 15. Constantin, D., Veres, D., Panaiotu, C., Anechitei-Deacu, V., Groza, S.M., Begy, R.,
723 Kelemen, S., Buylaert, J.-P., Hambach, U., Marković, S.B., Gerasimenko, N., Timar-
724 Gabor, A., 2019. Luminescence age constraints on the Pleistocene-Holocene transition
725 recorded in loess sequences across SE Europe. *Quat. Geochronol.* 49, 71-77.
726 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2018.07.011>.
- 727 16. Cook, E.R., Woodhouse, C.A., Eakin, C.M., Meko, D.M., Stahle, D.W., 2004. Long term
728 aridity changes in the western United States. *Science* 306, 1015-1018.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1102586>.

- 730 17. Cunningham, A.C., Wallinga, J., 2010. Selection of integration time intervals for quartz
731 OSL decay curves. *Quat. Geochronol.* 5, 657-666.
732 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2010.08.004>.
- 733 18. Denniston, R.F., DuPree, M., Dorale, J.A., Asmerom, Y., Polyak, V.J., Carpenter, S.J.,
734 2007. Episodes of late Holocene aridity recorded by stalagmites from Devil's Icebox
735 Cave, central Missouri, USA. *Quat. Res.* 68, 45-52.
736 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2007.04.001>.
- 737 19. Dearing, J.A., Dann, R.J.L., Hay, K., Lees, J.A., Loveland, P.J., Maher, B.A., O'Grady,
738 K., 1996. Frequency-dependent susceptibility measurements of environmental materials.
739 *Geophys. J. Int.* 124, 228-240. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.1996.tb06366.x>.
- 740 20. Dong, Y., Wu, N., Li, F., Huang, L., Wen, W., 2015. Time-transgressive nature of the
741 magnetic susceptibility record across the Chinese Loess Plateau at the Pleistocene/
742 Holocene transition. *PLoS One* 10, e0133541.
743 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0133541>.
- 744 21. Duller, G.A.T., 2003. Distinguishing quartz and feldspar in single grain luminescence
745 measurements. *Radiat. Meas.* 37, 161-165. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1350-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(02)00170-1)
746 [4487\(02\)00170-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(02)00170-1).
- 747 22. Eiler, J.M., 2007. "Clumped isotope" geochemistry—the study of naturally-occurring,
748 multiply-substituted isotopologues. *Earth Planet Sci. Lett.* 262, 309-327.
749 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2007.08.020>.
- 750 23. Feggestad, A.J., Jacobs, P.M., Miao, X., Mason, J.A., 2004. Stable carbon isotope record
751 of Holocene environmental change in the central Great Plains. *Physical Geography* 25,
752 170-190. <https://doi.org/10.2747/0272-3646.25.2.170>.
- 753 24. Galbraith, R.F., Roberts, R.G., 2012. Statistical aspects of equivalent dose and error
754 calculation and display in OSL dating: an overview and some recommendations. *Quat.*
755 *Geochronol.* 11, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2012.04.020>.
- 756 25. Galbraith, R.F., Roberts, R.G., Laslett, G.M., Yoshida, H., Olley, J.M., 1999. Optical
757 dating of single and multiple grains of quartz from Jinnium rock shelter, northern
758 Australia: part I, experimental design and statistical models. *Archaeometry* 41, 339-
759 364. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.1999.tb00987.x>.

- 760 26. Hansen, V., Murray, A., Buylaert, J.-P., Yeo, E.-Y., Thomsen, K., 2015. A new irradiated
761 quartz for beta source calibration. *Radiat. Meas.* 81, 123-127.
762 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2015.02.017>.
- 763 27. Jacobs, P.M., Mason, J.A., 2007. Late Quaternary climate change, loess sedimentation,
764 and soil profile development in the central Great Plains: A pedosedimentary model. *Geol.*
765 *Soc. Am. Bull.* 119, 462-475. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B25868.1>.
- 766 28. Jacobs, P.M., Mason, J.A., 2004. Paleopedology of soils in thick Holocene loess,
767 Nebraska, USA. *Rev. Mex. Cienc. Geol.* 21, 54-70.
- 768 29. Johnson, W.C., Willey, K.L., 2000. Isotopic and rock magnetic expression of
769 environmental change at the Pleistocene-Holocene transition in the central Great Plains.
770 *Quat. Int.* 67, 89-106. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(00\)00011-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(00)00011-2).
- 771 30. Lai, Z.P., Wintle, A.G., 2006. Locating the boundary between the Pleistocene and the
772 Holocene in Chinese loess using luminescence. *The Holocene* 16, 893-99.
773 <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683606hol980rr>.
- 774 31. Lapp, T., Kook, M., Murray, A.S., Thomsen, K.J., Buylaert, J.-P., Jain, M., 2015. A new
775 luminescence Detection and Stimulation Head for the Risø TL/OSL reader. *Radiat. Meas.*
776 81, 178-184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2015.02.001>.
- 777 32. Martin, C.W., 1993. Radiocarbon ages on late Pleistocene loess stratigraphy of Nebraska
778 and Kansas, Central Great Plains, U.S.A. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 12, 179-188.
779 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(93\)90052-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(93)90052-N).
- 780 33. Maat, P.B., Johnson, W.C., 1996. Thermoluminescence and new ¹⁴C age estimates for
781 late Quaternary loesses in southwestern Nebraska. *Geomorphology* 17, 115-128.
782 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-555X\(95\)00099-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-555X(95)00099-Q).
- 783 34. Marín-Spiotta, E., Chaopricha, N.T., Plante, A.F., Diefendorf, A.F., Mueller, C.W.,
784 Grandy, A.S., Mason, J.A., 2014. Long-term stabilization of deep soil carbon by fire and
785 burial during early Holocene climate change. *Nature Geoscience* 6, 428-432.
786 <https://doi.org/10.1038/NGEO2169>.
- 787 35. Marković, S.B., Sümeği, P., Stevens, T., Schaetzl, R.J., Obreht, I., Chu, W., Buggle, B.,
788 Zech, M., Zech, R., Zeeden, C., Gavrilov, M.B., Perić, Z., Svirčev, Z., Lehmkuhl, F.,
789 2018. The Crvenka loess-paleosol sequence: A record of continuous grassland

- 790 domination during the Late Pleistocene, for the southern Carpathian Basin. *Palaeogeogr.*
791 *Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* 509, 33-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2018.03.019>.
- 792 36. Marković, S.B., Timar-Gabor, A., Stevens, T., Hambach, U., Popov, D., Tomić, N.,
793 Obreht, I., Jovanović, M., Lehmkuhl, F., Kels, H., Marković, R., Gavrilov, M.B., 2014.
794 Environmental dynamics and luminescence chronology from the Orlovat loess–palaeosol
795 sequence (Vojvodina, northern Serbia). *J. Quat. Sci.* 29, 189-199.
796 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.2693>.
- 797 37. Martin, C.W., 1993. Radiocarbon ages on late Pleistocene loess stratigraphy of Nebraska
798 and Kansas, central Great Plains, U.S.A. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 12, 179-188.
799 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(93\)90052-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(93)90052-N).
- 800 38. Mason, J.A., Jacobs, P.M., Hanson, P.R., Miao, X., Goble, R.J., 2003. Sources and
801 paleoclimatic significance of Holocene Bignell Loess, central Great Plains, USA. *Quat.*
802 *Res.* 60, 330-339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2003.07.005>.
- 803 39. Mason, J.A., Kuzila, M.S., 2000. Episodic Holocene loess deposition in central Nebraska:
804 *Quat. Int.* 67, 119-131. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(00\)00013-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(00)00013-6).
- 805 40. Mason, J.A., Joeckel, R.M., Bettis, E.A., III, 2007. Middle to Late Pleistocene loess
806 record in eastern Nebraska, USA, and implications for the unique nature of Oxygen
807 Isotope Stage 2: *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 26, 773-792.
808 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2006.10.007>
- 809 41. Mason, J.A., Miao, X.D., Hanson, P.R., Johnson, W.C., Jacobs, P.M., Goble, R. J., 2008.
810 Loess record of the Pleistocene-Holocene transition on the northern and central Great
811 Plains, USA. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 27, 1772-1783.
812 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2008.07.004>.
- 813 42. Mason, J.A., Greene, R.S.B., Joeckel, R.M., 2011. Laser diffraction analysis of the
814 disintegration of aeolian sedimentary aggregates in water. *CATENA* 87, 107-118.
815 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2011.05.015>.
- 816 43. May, D.W., Holen, S.R., 1993. Radiocarbon ages of soils and charcoal in late
817 Wisconsinan loess, South-Central Nebraska. *Quat. Res.* 39, 55-58.
818 <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1993.1006>.
- 819 44. Mejdahl, V., 1979. Thermoluminescence dating: beta-dose attenuation in quartz grains.
820 *Archaeometry* 21, 61-72.

- 821 45. Miao, X., Mason, J.A., Goble, R.J., Hanson, P.R., 2005. Loess record of dry climate and
822 aeolian activity in the early-to mid-Holocene, central Great Plains, North America. *The*
823 *Holocene* 15, 339-346. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683605hl805rp>.
- 824 46. Miao, X., Mason, J.A., Johnson, W.C., Wang, H., 2007a. High-resolution proxy record of
825 Holocene climate from a loess section in Southwestern Nebraska, USA. *Palaeogeogr.*
826 *Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* 245, 368-381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2006.09.004>.
- 827 47. Miao, X.D., Mason, J.A., Swinehart, J.B., Loope, D.B., Hanson, P.R., Goble, R.J., Liu,
828 X.D., 2007b. A 10,000-yr record of dune activity, dust storms, and severe drought in the
829 central Great Plains, U.S.A. *Geology* 35, 119-122. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G23133A.1>.
- 830 48. Monger, H.C., Cole, D.R., Buck, B.J., Gallegos, R.A., 2009. Scale and the isotopic record
831 of C₄ plants in pedogenic carbonate: from the biome to the rhizosphere. *Ecology* 90,
832 1498-1511. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-0670.1>.
- 833 49. Muhs, D.R., Aleinikoff, J.N., Stafford, T.W., Jr., Kihl, R., Been, J., Mahan, S.A.,
834 Cowherd, S., 1999. Late Quaternary loess in northeastern Colorado: Part I. Age and
835 paleoclimatic significance. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 111, 1861-1875.
836 [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1999\)111<1861:LQLINC>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1999)111<1861:LQLINC>2.3.CO;2).
- 837 50. Muhs, D.R., Bettis III, E.A., Aleinikoff, J., McGeehin, J.P., Beann, J., Skipp, G.,
838 Marshall, B.D., Roberts, H.M., Johnson, W.C., Benton, R., 2008. Origin and
839 paleoclimatic significance of late Quaternary loess in Nebraska: evidence from
840 stratigraphy, chronology, sedimentology and geochemistry. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.*
841 120, 1378-1407. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B26221.1>.
- 842 51. Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2000. Luminescence dating of quartz using an improved
843 single-aliquot regenerative-dose protocol. *Radiat. Meas.* 32, 57-73.
844 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(99\)00253-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(99)00253-X).
- 845 52. Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2003. The single aliquot regenerative dose protocol:
846 potential for improvements in reliability. *Radiat. Meas.* 37, 377-381.
847 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(03)00053-2).
- 848 53. Prescott, J.R., Hutton, J.T., 1994. Cosmic ray contributions to dose rates for
849 luminescence and ESR dating: large depths and long term variations. *Radiat. Meas.* 23,
850 497-500. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-4487\(94\)90086-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-4487(94)90086-8).

- 851 54. Pigati, J. S., McGeehin, J. P., Muhs, D. R., Bettis, E. A., 2013. Radiocarbon dating late
852 Quaternary loess deposits using small terrestrial gastropod shells, *Quat. Sci. Rev.*, 76,
853 114–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2013.05.013>.
- 854 55. Pye, K., 1987. *Aeolian dust and dust deposits*. Academic Press, London, 334 pp.
- 855 56. Pye, K., Winspear, N.R., Zhou, L.P., 1995. Thermoluminescence ages of loess and
856 associated sediments in central Nebraska, USA. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol.*
857 *Palaeoecol.* 118, 73-87. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(94\)00134-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(94)00134-T).
- 858 57. Quade, J., Cerling, T.E., Bowman, J.R., 1989. Systematic variations in the carbon and
859 oxygen isotopic compositions of pedogenic carbonate along elevation transects in the
860 southern Great Basin, United States. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 101, 464-475.
861 [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1989\)101<0464:SVITCA>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1989)101<0464:SVITCA>2.3.CO;2).
- 862 58. Rees-Jones, J., 1995. Optical dating of young sediments using fine-grain quartz. *Ancient*
863 *TL* 13, 9-13.
- 864 59. Roberts, H.M., Muhs, D.R., Wintle, A.G., Duller, G.A.T., Bettis III, E.A., 2003.
865 Unprecedented last glacial mass accumulation rates determined by luminescence dating
866 of loess from western Nebraska. *Quat. Res.* 59, 411-419. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0033-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0033-5894(03)00040-1)
867 [5894\(03\)00040-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0033-5894(03)00040-1).
- 868 60. Schultz, C.B., Stout, T.M., 1948. Pleistocene mammals and terraces in the Great Plains.
869 *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 59, 541-630.
- 870 61. Shuman, B.N., Marsicek, J., 2016. The structure of Holocene climate change in mid-
871 latitude North America. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 141, 38-51.
872 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.03.009>.
- 873 62. Stevens, T., Armitage, S.J., Lu, H.Y., Thomas, D.S.G., 2006. Sedimentation and
874 diagenesis of Chinese loess: implications for the preservation of continuous, high-
875 resolution climate records. *Geology* 34, 849-852. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G22472.1>.
- 876 63. Stevens, T., Markovic, S.B., Zech, M., Hambach, U., Sümegei, P., 2011. Dust deposition
877 and climate in the Carpathian Basin over an independently dated last glacial-interglacial
878 cycle. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 30, 662-681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2010.12.011>.
- 879 64. Thomsen, K.J., Bøtter-Jensen, L., Denby, P.M., Moska, P., Murray, A.S., 2006.
880 Developments in luminescence measurement techniques. *Radiat. Meas.* 41, 768-773.
881 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2006.06.010>.

- 882 65. Timar-Gabor, A., Vandenberghe, D.A.G., Vasiliniuc, S., Panaoitu, C. E., Panaiotu, C. G.,
883 Dimofte, D., Cosma, C. 2011. Optical dating of Romanian Loess a comparison between
884 silt-sized and sand-sized quartz. *Quat. Int.*, 240, 62-70.
885 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2010.10.007>
- 886 66. Timar-Gabor, A. Constantin, D., Marković, S.B., Jain, M., 2015. Extending the area of
887 investigation of fine versus coarse quartz optical ages from the Lower Danube to the
888 Carpathian Basin. *Quat. Int.*, 388, 168-176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.09.065>
- 889 67. Timar-Gabor, A., Buylaert, J-P., Guralnik, B., Trandafir-Antohei, O., Constantin, D.,
890 Anechitei-Deacu, V., Jain, M., Murray, A.S., Porat, N., Hao, Q., Wintle, A.G., 2017. On
891 the importance of grain size in luminescence dating using quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 106, 464-
892 471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2017.01.009>
- 893 68. Újvári, G., Kok, J.F., Varga, G., Kovács, J., 2016. The physics of wind-blown loess:
894 Implications for grain size proxy interpretations in Quaternary paleoclimate studies.
895 *Earth-Sci. Rev.* 154, 247-278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.01.006>.
- 896 69. Vandenberghe, D.A.G., De Corte, F., Buylaert, J.-P., Kucera, J., Van den haute, P., 2008.
897 On the internal radioactivity in quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 43, 771-775.
898 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2008.01.016>.
- 899 70. Woodburn, T.L., Johnson, W.C., Mason, J.A., Bozarth, S.R., Halfen, A.F. 2017.
900 Vegetation dynamics during the Pleistocene-Holocene transition in the central Great
901 Plains, USA. *The Holocene* 27, 155-163. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683616652710>.
- 902 71. Yang, Y., Mason, J.A., Zhang, H., Lu, H., Ji, J., Chen, J., Liu, L., 2017. Provenance of
903 loess in the central Great Plains, U.S.A., based on Nd-Sr isotopic composition, and
904 paleoenvironmental implications. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 173, 114-123.
905 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.08.009>.
- 906 72. Zhao, G.Y., Liu, X.M., Chen, Q., Lü, B., Niu, H.W., Liu, Z., Li, P. Y., 2013.
907 Paleoclimatic evolution of Holocene loess and discussion of the sensitivity of magnetic
908 susceptibility and median diameter. *Quat. Int.* 296, 160-167.
909 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2012.06.015>
- 924 73. ~~Timar-Gabor, A., Buylaert, J.-P., Guralnik, B., Trandafir-Antohei, O., Constantin, D., Anechitei-Deacu, V., Jain, M., Murray, A.S., Porat, N., Hao, Q., Wintle, A.G., 2017. On the importance of grain size in luminescence dating using quartz. Radiat. Meas. 106, 464-471. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2017.01.009~~

Figure 1. (a) State of Nebraska, USA, within the Great Plains Ecoregion (gray shade).

Figure 1. (b) Location of Enders and Wauneta study sites within landscape of Chase County, Nebraska. Light gray areas are sand dunes and sand sheets; areas of thick loess forming tablelands are labeled, along with study sites and the two villages of the same names.

Figure 2. Stratigraphy and weighted average ages of the Enders sequence as well as the stratigraphy of Wauneta section from **Miao et al. (2007a)**.

Figure 3. Stratigraphy, weighted average ages and grain size variations with depth at Enders site (gray and black lines indicate data from upper and lower profiles, respectively). Data are compared with the <16 μm fraction variation at Wauneta section (Miao et al. 2007a). Dashed lines denote correlation of the grain size pattern of the three buried soils identified in the two sites. Note the three peaks of fine material (labeled 1, 2, 3) at similar stratigraphic positions above and within Brady Soil.

Figure 4. Stratigraphy, weighted average ages, low-frequency magnetic susceptibility and frequency dependence of magnetic susceptibility at Enders site.

Figure 5. Stratigraphy, weighted average ages, carbon and oxygen isotopic compositions of bulk carbonate at Enders site (black and gray lines indicate data from upper and lower profiles, respectively). Data are compared with carbon isotopic compositions of organic matter from Wauneta (Miao et al. 2007a). Dashed lines indicate correlative soil horizons at the two sites. Higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of organic matter at Wauneta records greater proportion of C_4 plant biomass, which should also lead to higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in pedogenic carbonate formed *in situ*.

Figure 6. Representative sensitivity-corrected growth curve constructed for (a), (d) 4-11 μm , (b), (e) 63-90 μm and (c), (f) 90-125 μm quartz fractions from END 1.2 and END 1.10 samples. The responses to regenerated doses are shown as open squares. The sensitivity corrected natural signal is depicted as a star and the equivalent dose is indicated by an arrow. Recycling and IR depletion points are represented as an open triangle and an open down triangle, respectively. The inset shows a typical decay curve of natural CW-OSL signal (open squares) in comparison to a regenerated signal (open circles) and a calibration quartz signal (open triangles).

Supplementary material

Supplementary Table S1. The measured equivalent doses (ED) along with the performance parameters of the SAR protocol for each quartz grain-size of the 12 samples analyzed. The number of aliquots averaged for ED calculations is also given. Quoted errors represent 1σ .

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	ED (Gy)	Recycling ratio	Recuperation (%)	IR depletion ratio
END 1.1	77	4-11	3.1 ± 0.1 (n=13)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.50 ± 0.47	0.94 ± 0.01
		63-90	2.3 ± 0.0 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	1.62 ± 0.29	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	2.3 ± 0.2 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.34	0.99 ± 0.01
END 1.2	147	4-11	10.1 ± 0.6 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.13	0.95 ± 0.01
		63-90	8.2 ± 0.2 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	7.8 ± 0.2 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.18	1.00 ± 0.01
END 1.3	207	4-11	10.7 ± 0.3 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.13	0.95 ± 0.01
		63-90	8.9 ± 0.1 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.05	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	8.9 ± 0.3 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.09	0.99 ± 0.01
END 1.4	307	4-11	14.6 ± 0.3 (n=10)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.09	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	12.1 ± 0.2 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.07	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	12.2 ± 0.4 (n=11)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.01
END 1.5	398	4-11	29.0 ± 0.7 (n=13)	0.98 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.06	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	25.0 ± 1.1 (n=10)	1.05 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	22.0 ± 0.6 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.01
END 1.6	455	4-11	29.6 ± 0.3 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01
		63-90	30.6 ± 1.1 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	23.8 ± 0.8 (n=10)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.01
END 1.7	506	4-11	43.4 ± 0.8 (n=12)	0.96 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.05	0.95 ± 0.01
		63-90	33.5 ± 0.7 (n=20)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	35.7 ± 1.3 (n=10)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.01
END 1.8	546	4-11	47.3 ± 0.8 (n=10)	1.00 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.01
		63-90	42.3 ± 0.5 (n=58)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	-	-	-	-
END 1.9	564	4-11	57.4 ± 0.3 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		63-90	45.4 ± 0.8 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	47.5 ± 0.4 (n=10)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.01
END 1.10	579	4-11	58.0 ± 0.3 (n=11)	1.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01
		63-90	49.3 ± 0.9 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01
		90-125	52.0 ± 0.9 (n=11)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.01
END 1.11	601	4-11	51.8 ± 0.6 (n=11)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	49.9 ± 1.1 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.05	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	49.0 ± 0.9 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01
END 1.12	649	4-11	60.0 ± 0.6 (n=10)	1.02 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01
		63-90	55.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)	1.01 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.01
		90-125	52.4 ± 0.9 (n=11)	1.03 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.01

Supplementary Table S2. OSL ages calculated assuming different past moisture scenarios. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to Aitken (1985).

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Water content as found (%)	Grain size (μm)	Age (ka) (As found water content)	Weighted ages (ka) (As found water content)	Age (ka) (5% water content)	Weighted ages (ka) (5% water content)	Age (ka) (10% water content)	Weighted ages (ka) (10% water content)
END 1.1	77	1.1	4-11	0.7 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.0
			63-90	0.6 ± 0.0		0.6 ± 0.0		0.7 ± 0.0	
			90-125	0.6 ± 0.1		0.6 ± 0.1		0.7 ± 0.1	
END 1.2	147	1.7	4-11	2.3 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.2
			63-90	2.2 ± 0.1		2.3 ± 0.1		2.4 ± 0.2	
			90-125	2.1 ± 0.1		2.2 ± 0.1		2.3 ± 0.2	
END 1.3	207	2.2	4-11	2.5 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.2	2.7 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.2
			63-90	2.4 ± 0.1		2.5 ± 0.1		2.6 ± 0.2	
			90-125	2.4 ± 0.1		2.5 ± 0.1		2.6 ± 0.2	
END 1.4	307	2.7	4-11	3.1 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.2
			63-90	3.0 ± 0.2		3.1 ± 0.2		3.3 ± 0.2	
			90-125	3.1 ± 0.2		3.2 ± 0.2		3.4 ± 0.2	
END 1.5	398	4.2	4-11	6.5 ± 0.5	6.2 ± 0.4	6.5 ± 0.5	6.3 ± 0.4	6.9 ± 0.6	6.7 ± 0.5
			63-90	6.6 ± 0.5		6.7 ± 0.5		7.1 ± 0.5	
			90-125	5.9 ± 0.4		6.0 ± 0.4		6.3 ± 0.4	
END 1.6	455	3.9	4-11	6.9 ± 0.5	6.8 ± 0.4	7.0 ± 0.5	6.9 ± 0.5	7.4 ± 0.6	7.2 ± 0.5
			63-90	8.5 ± 0.6		8.6 ± 0.6		9.1 ± 0.7	
			90-125	6.7 ± 0.5		6.8 ± 0.5		7.1 ± 0.5	
END 1.7	506	5.4	4-11	10.0 ± 0.8	9.5 ± 0.6	9.9 ± 0.8	9.5 ± 0.6	10.5 ± 0.9	10.0 ± 0.7
			63-90	9.1 ± 0.6		9.1 ± 0.6		9.6 ± 0.6	
			90-125	9.8 ± 0.7		9.8 ± 0.7		10.3 ± 0.8	
END 1.8	546	6.7	4-11	11.1 ± 0.9	11.5 ± 0.8	10.9 ± 0.9	11.3 ± 0.8	11.5 ± 1.0	11.9 ± 0.8
			63-90	11.8 ± 0.7		11.6 ± 0.7		12.2 ± 0.8	
			90-125	-		-		-	
END 1.9	564	7.3	4-11	13.2 ± 1.1	12.9 ± 0.8	12.9 ± 1.0	12.5 ± 0.8	13.6 ± 1.1	13.2 ± 0.9
			63-90	12.4 ± 0.8		12.1 ± 0.7		12.8 ± 0.8	
			90-125	13.2 ± 0.8		12.8 ± 0.8		13.5 ± 0.9	
END 1.10	579	4.9	4-11	12.2 ± 1.0	12.7 ± 0.8	12.2 ± 1.0	12.8 ± 0.8	12.9 ± 1.1	13.4 ± 0.9

			63-90	12.5 ± 0.8		12.5 ± 0.8		13.2 ± 0.9	
			90-125	13.3 ± 0.8		13.4 ± 0.8		14.1 ± 0.9	
END 1.11	601	2.0	4-11	11.9 ± 0.9	13.1 ± 0.8	12.3 ± 1.0	13.6 ± 0.9	13.0 ± 1.1	14.3 ± 1.0
			63-90	13.6 ± 0.8		14.1 ± 0.9		14.8 ± 1.0	
			90-125	13.5 ± 0.8		14.0 ± 0.9		14.8 ± 1.0	
END 1.12	649	4.7	4-11	13.4 ± 1.1	14.0 ± 0.9	13.5 ± 1.1	14.1 ± 0.9	14.2 ± 1.2	14.9 ± 1.0
			63-90	14.6 ± 1.1		14.7 ± 1.1		15.5 ± 1.2	
			90-125	14.1 ± 0.9		14.1 ± 0.9		14.9 ± 1.0	

Supplementary Figure S1. (a) Upper and (b) lower profiles of Enders section.

Supplementary Figure S2. Dose recovery test results for fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fractions from samples END 1.4, END 1.6, END 1.8, END 1.10 and END.12. The given irradiation doses were chosen to match the equivalent dose of each sample. The solid line indicates the ideal 1:1 dose recovery ratio while the dash lines bracket a 10% variation from unity.

Supplementary Figure S3. Equivalent dose dependence on preheat temperatures for fine and coarse quartz fractions from sample END 1.8. A 180°C cutheat (test dose preheat) was employed.

Supplementary Figure S4. Frequency histogram of the equivalent doses values obtained for coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fraction from sample END 1.8.

END 1.8 (63-90 μm)

n = 58 | in 2 sigma = 67.2 %

Supplementary Figure S5. Radial plot of the equivalent doses values obtained for coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fraction from sample END 1.8.

Table 1. Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . The ages were determined considering the “as found” water content, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm fractions are 0.94 ± 0.050 and 0.92 ± 0.050 , respectively; adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	Water content (% dry mass)	ED (Gy)	U-Ra* (Bq/kg)	Th (Bq/kg)	K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)	Total systematic error (%)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)	Weighted ages (ka)
END 1.1	77	4-11	1.1	3.1 ± 0.1 (n=13)	43.8 \pm 1.1	44.4 \pm 1.3	613 \pm 16	3.5	7.6	4.60 \pm 0.07	0.7 \pm 0.1	0.6 \pm 0.0
		63-90		2.3 ± 0.0 (n=10)				2.6	5.4	3.87 \pm 0.06	0.6 \pm 0.0	
		90-125		2.3 ± 0.2 (n=10)				8.8	5.4	3.83 \pm 0.06	0.6 \pm 0.1	
END 1.2	147	4-11	1.7	10.1 ± 0.6 (n=10)	40.2 \pm 1.5	39.8 \pm 1.2	622 \pm 18	6.2	7.4	4.37 \pm 0.07	2.3 \pm 0.2	2.2 \pm 0.1
		63-90		8.2 ± 0.2 (n=10)				3.0	5.4	3.70 \pm 0.07	2.2 \pm 0.1	
		90-125		7.8 ± 0.2 (n=11)				3.1	5.4	3.65 \pm 0.06	2.1 \pm 0.1	
END 1.3	207	4-11	2.2	10.7 ± 0.3 (n=11)	38.5 \pm 1.7	39.6 \pm 1.2	646 \pm 16	3.2	7.3	4.36 \pm 0.07	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.4 \pm 0.1
		63-90		8.9 ± 0.1 (n=10)				2.0	5.5	3.70 \pm 0.06	2.4 \pm 0.1	
		90-125		8.9 ± 0.3 (n=10)				2.0	5.4	3.66 \pm 0.06	2.4 \pm 0.1	
END 1.4	307	4-11	2.7	14.6 ± 0.3 (n=10)	41.5 \pm 1.2	41.6 \pm 0.5	715 \pm 18	2.5	7.2	4.68 \pm 0.06	3.1 \pm 0.2	3.1 \pm 0.2
		63-90		12.1 ± 0.2 (n=10)				2.2	5.5	3.98 \pm 0.06	3.0 \pm 0.2	
		90-125		12.2 ± 0.4 (n=11)				3.6	5.5	3.92 \pm 0.06	3.1 \pm 0.2	
END 1.5	398	4-11	4.2	29.0 ± 0.7 (n=13)	44.8 \pm 1.5	41.2 \pm 1.2	656 \pm 17	2.9	7.6	4.46 \pm 0.07	6.5 \pm 0.5	6.2 \pm 0.4
		63-90		25.0 ± 1.1 (n=10)				4.7	5.6	3.77 \pm 0.06	6.6 \pm 0.5	
		90-125		22.0 ± 0.6 (n=10)				3.2	5.6	3.72 \pm 0.06	5.9 \pm 0.4	
END 1.6	455	4-11	3.9	29.6 ± 0.3 (n=10)	40.9 \pm 1.5	39.9 \pm 1.2	634 \pm 19	2.0	7.5	4.26 \pm 0.08	6.9 \pm 0.5	6.8 \pm 0.4
		63-90		30.6 ± 1.1 (n=10)				4.0	5.6	3.61 \pm 0.07	8.5 \pm 0.6	
		90-125		23.8 ± 0.8 (n=10)				3.8	5.6	3.56 \pm 0.07	6.7 \pm 0.5	
END 1.7	506	4-11	5.4	43.4 ± 0.8 (n=12)	40.0 \pm 0.9	44.4 \pm 0.7	658 \pm 17	2.3	7.6	4.34 \pm 0.06	10.0 \pm 0.8	9.5 \pm 0.6
		63-90		33.5 ± 0.7 (n=20)				2.6	5.7	3.67 \pm 0.05	9.1 \pm 0.6	
		90-125		35.7 ± 1.3 (n=10)				3.9	5.7	3.63 \pm 0.05	9.8 \pm 0.7	

END 1.8	546	4-11	6.7	47.3 ± 0.8 (n=10)	44.2±1.8	43.9±1.2	627±18	2.4	7.9	4.27 ± 0.07	11.1 ± 0.9	11.5 ± 0.8
		63-90		42.3 ± 0.5 (n=58)				2.1	5.8	3.60 ± 0.06	11.8 ± 0.7	
		90-125		-				-	-	-		
END 1.9	564	4-11	7.3	57.4 ± 0.3 (n=11)	46.2±0.3	42.1±0.5	653±20	1.5	7.9	4.33 ± 0.06	13.2 ± 1.1	12.9 ± 0.8
		63-90		45.4 ± 0.8 (n=10)				2.4	5.9	3.66 ± 0.06	12.4 ± 0.8	
		90-125		47.5 ± 0.4 (n=10)				1.8	5.8	3.61 ± 0.06	13.2 ± 0.8	
END 1.10	579	4-11	4.9	58.0 ± 0.3 (n=11)	54.3±0.4	48.1±1.5	634±20	1.6	8.1	4.74 ± 0.07	12.2 ± 1.0	12.7 ± 0.8
		63-90		49.3 ± 0.9 (n=10)				2.5	5.6	3.95 ± 0.07	12.5 ± 0.8	
		90-125		52.0 ± 0.9 (n=11)				2.4	5.6	3.90 ± 0.07	13.3 ± 0.8	
END 1.11	601	4-11	2.0	51.8 ± 0.6 (n=11)	42.0±1.9	43.9±0.6	606±19	2.1	7.7	4.37 ± 0.08	11.9 ± 0.9	13.1 ± 0.8
		63-90		49.9 ± 1.1 (n=10)				2.9	5.5	3.67 ± 0.07	13.6 ± 0.8	
		90-125		49.0 ± 0.9 (n=10)				2.6	5.5	3.62 ± 0.07	13.5 ± 0.8	
END 1.12	649	4-11	4.7	60.0 ± 0.6 (n=10)	43.8±0.8	44.4±0.9	661±21	1.9	7.7	4.47 ± 0.07	13.4 ± 1.1	14.0 ± 0.9
		63-90		55.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)				4.5	5.6	3.77 ± 0.07	14.6 ± 1.1	
		90-125		52.4 ± 0.9 (n=11)				2.5	5.6	3.72 ± 0.07	14.1 ± 0.9	

*U-Ra is the equivalent uranium concentration deduced from ^{226}Ra activity, considering the secular equilibrium between ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra .